

COGNITIVE-METAPHORICAL ANALYSIS OF
UZBEKISTAN PHRASEOLOGISMS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the semantic and conceptual interpretation of phraseological units in the Uzbek language based on the theory of cognitive metaphor. Phraseologisms are studied as metaphorical models expressing the worldview of the people, and their conceptual maps are formed. Phraseologisms in the Uzbek language are analyzed based on the theory of cognitive metaphor. It is highlighted how phraseological units create meaning through conceptual metaphors, how they reflect national-cultural perceptions, and how they form the worldview of the speaker of the language. Conceptual models are developed based on the theory of metaphor (Lakoff, Johnson, Kövecses) and the phraseological base of the Uzbek language. The study analyzes metaphorical phraseologisms expressing human activity, body parts, emotions, and movement as examples.

Language is the most subtle and deepest mirror of human thinking. It embodies the life experience, worldview, spiritual world, feelings and, most importantly, the model of how the people perceive the world, formed over the centuries. The Uzbek language has a rich and diverse phraseological heritage, and these units are of particular scientific importance not only as an artistic tool, but also as cognitive phenomena expressing the system of conceptual representations existing in the human mind. Phraseologisms are not simple expressions that adorn the artistic layer of the language. They are figurative units that embody the historical memory, spiritual world, aesthetics, and philosophy of life of the nation.

The cognitive-metaphorical approach allows us to reveal the inner meaning of these units, to explain the conceptual structures hidden in them. First of all, it is important to have a brief understanding of what the word cognitive is and what it means. What is cognition? Cognition is a complex of human processes of knowing, understanding, perceiving, remembering, understanding, thinking, and processing information. Cognitive processes determine how a person perceives the environment, what meaning he gives to it, and how he expresses that meaning through language. Cognitive sciences study the mechanisms of the human mind, combining such fields as psychology, linguistics, philosophy, neurology, and anthropology. Concepts related to the body, nature, space, movement, light, and colors are one of the main cognitive sources of phraseologisms, through which the national worldview of the

Uzbek language becomes clearer. We will analyze this cognitive-metaphorical process on the basis of Uzbek phraseologisms.

Phraseologisms - in language, they are often formed on a metaphorical basis, that is, a similarity or associative connection is formed between two areas that are not close to each other in terms of content. Through metaphor, abstract, complex or concepts related to internal experiences are expressed through concrete, sensory images. Phraseologisms often seem far from their true meaning with their external form, but behind them is hidden a whole conceptual world formed in human thinking. Each of the expressions such as “to brighten up”, “to feel a pang in the heart”, “to have two heads”, “to have a nut on the head”, “to have a blow to the soul”, “to raise the head”, “to put a foot on the face” is formed on the basis of a certain metaphorical model. In these expressions, the feelings of lightening, freezing of the heart, or heartache actually stem from the instinct of a person to express his spiritual experiences through physical sensations. This process reveals the nature of cognitive metaphors. The following stages are usually considered in the metaphorical analysis of phraseologisms:

Determination of the main context domain (Source domain). This is the source of the image of the phraseologism, which is related to the daily life experience of a person:

body parts (to brighten)

physical movements (to raise the head)

Determination of the target domain. This is the abstract meaning expressed by the phraseologism: emotion, mood, behavior, attitude, etc. For example: “to brighten” - relief of feelings, getting the expected result after some event, joy.

Determination of the metaphorical mechanism. At this stage, the similarity or associative connection is explained: Light - joy, weight - anxiety, high - good, joy, low - bad, depression, hot - affection, cold - indifference.

Definition of a conceptual metaphor. It is determined which main conceptual metaphor the phraseologism belongs to: For example: To rise like a mountain - a metaphor of emotion, meaning good mood, joy; To be confused - a metaphor of physical action, meaning thinking, reasoning; To freeze - a metaphor of emotional coldness of a person and is considered an emotional metaphor.

From the point of view of cognitive linguistics, phraseologisms are the linguistic manifestation of conceptual metaphors existing in the human mind. That is, behind the superficial form of phraseologism lies a deep spiritual-imaginative system based on human experience. According to the cognitive-metaphorical approach, in order to understand complex, abstract concepts encountered in life, a person associates them with familiar, visible, and intuitively perceived objects. Therefore, concepts such as light, temperature, height, space, natural phenomena, and body parts play a key role in Uzbek phraseologisms. For example, the illumination of the soul - a person's joy, spiritual lightness is conceptualized through light; the freezing of the heart - a state of fear, anguish, and indifference is expressed through the concept of coldness; and the clouding of the soul is manifested in combination with weather images of depression. These images deeply reflect the traces of conceptual metaphors in the folk worldview, such as “Goodness is light”, “Evil is darkness”, “Love is heat”, “Depression is darkness”, “Joy is height”. According to the cognitive approach, a person understands the world not only through language, but also through his experience, imagination and concepts

in his mind. Language is a coded form of these concepts. Metaphor, symbol, image, phraseologisms are the manifestation of the knowledge system in the mind through language. Therefore, cognition in language learning is related to how a person thinks, through what associations he creates meaning, and how he conceptualizes the world. According to cognitive linguistics, in particular, the “conceptual metaphor theory” put forward by Lakoff and Johnson: The main elements of cognition are as follows. Perception is the perception of the external world through the senses. Most phraseologisms are formed precisely on the basis of perception: being heavy, light, cold, heat, etc. Concepts are generalized, abstract forms of knowledge in the mind, and phraseologisms are active in concepts such as: soul, heart, road, light, height, sun. Categorization is the process by which a person divides objects into categories based on experience. For example, “light” is “good”, “darkness” is “bad”. Metaphor and metonymy are the most important cognitive mechanisms for creating meaning. In metaphor, meaning is transferred based on similarity, in metonymy, on proximity. Conceptual maps are a system of organizing meanings in the mind: “heart is the center of emotions”, “head is the center of reason”. Metaphor is not a speech ornament, but a conceptual system that determines how a person thinks.

Phraseologisms in the Uzbek language are figurative language units that reflect the centuries-old life experience, worldview, cultural values, and national thinking of the people. They are not only an artistic tool, but also a manifestation of conceptual metaphors formed in the human mind in the form of language. This aspect is directly related to cognitive-metaphorical theory. In the Uzbek mentality, national concepts such as “heart”, “honor”, “honor”, “blessing”, “fate” are especially valued and find their unique variety in phraseologisms. The breadth of the heart is associated with virtue, the fall of the heart is described as a decrease in value, and stepping on the face means a violation of respect. These expressions are not only a means of meaning, but also cognitive-cultural phenomena that reflect how the people imagine the world and what values they prioritize.

The metaphorical analysis of phraseologisms shows that many expressions in the Uzbek language are linguistic expressions of conceptual metaphors that arose on the basis of a person’s everyday experience, sensations and life observations. Metaphor in phraseologisms is manifested not only as an artistic tool, but also as an intellectual system, a model of thinking. Therefore, phraseologisms are a figurative mirror of the national mentality. Thus, the cognitive-metaphorical analysis of Uzbek phraseologisms is extremely important not only for linguistics, but also for studying the psyche, culture and worldview of the people. Phraseologisms are the spiritual depth of the language, the brightest reflection of the nation’s thinking. Each of them embodies a thousand-year experience, a spiritual layer, artistic elevation and a deep expression of cognitive thinking.

References:

1. Apresyan, Y.D. Leksik ma’no va konseptual tizim. – Moskva: Nauka, 1995.
2. Kövecses, Z. Metaphor: A Practical Introduction. – Oxford University Press, 2010.
3. Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. Metaphors We Live By. – Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980.
4. Mamatov, A. O‘zbek tilida frazeologik birliklarning semantik xususiyatlari. – Toshkent: Fan, 2008.

5. Nazarov, T. Til va tafakkur munosabati. – Toshkent: Universitet, 2004.
6. Ortiqov, A. O‘zbek frazeologiyasi bo‘yicha tadqiqotlar. – Toshkent: Fan, 1999.
7. Rahmatullayev, Sh. O‘zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug‘ati. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 1992.
8. Safarov, Sh. Kognitiv lingvistika asoslari. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2006.

